

**Formation Constants of Aluminium(III),
Indium(III) and Gallium(III) Complexes
with some Schiff Bases**

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COMPLEXING tendencies of Schiff bases, derived from 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB) with aniline (FHM BANIL), paramethyl aniline (FHMBMANIL) and parachloroaniline (FHMBCANIL) with transition and inner-transition metal ions have been reported earlier^{1,2}. In the present investigation the interaction of these ligands with Al^{III}, In^{III} and Ga^{III} has been followed pH-metrically.

Experimental

The Schiff bases FHM BANIL, FHMBMANIL¹ and FHMBCANIL² were prepared by refluxing (1 h) equimolar quantities of FHMB and the respective anilines in methanol. The solids separated were crystallised from methanol to get tlc-pure samples. The metal ion solutions were prepared using metal nitrates (AnalaR) in conductance water and standardised.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants were determined using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique³ in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water ($I=0.1M$ NaClO₄) at 35° and the pH meter readings (B) were corrected⁴.

Results and Discussion

The pH-titration curves of FHM BANIL and FHMBMANIL indicated the presence of a protonation centre, viz. tertiary nitrogen of azomethine group and a dissociable phenolic OH group in conformity with the observations made earlier². However the azomethine nitrogen of FHMBCANIL is so acidic that its pH titration curve showed only the basic buffer region corresponding to the dissociation of phenolic proton.

The values of $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated³ with necessary volume corrections. From the proton-ligand formation curves the log K_{OH} and log K_{NH^+} corresponding to the phenolic and azomethine groups of these Schiff bases were evaluated by different computational methods³. The values are consistent with each other. The azomethine group in these Schiff bases is found to be significantly basic and this can be due to the base strengthening mesomeric effect of phenolic OH group. The relative increase in the log K_{OH} and log K_{NH^+} values (Table 1) of FHMBMANIL over FHM BANIL is due to the electron-donating property of methyl group. The decreasing value in FHMBCANIL can be due to the electron-withdrawing effect of Cl-group.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL SCHIFF BASES IN 70% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL

Temp. = 35°, $I = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

Metal	Constant	FHMBANIL	FHMBMANIL	FHMBCANIL
H ⁺	log K_{OH}	8.30	8.92	7.31
	log K_{NH^+}	3.40	3.50	—
Al ^{III}	log K_1	6.93	7.68	5.37
	log K_2	5.93	6.60	5.05
In ^{III}	log K_1	7.31	8.56	5.61
	log K_2	6.35	7.02	5.55
Ga ^{III}	log K_1	7.87	8.76	6.17
	log K_2	6.71	7.99	5.68

The metal-ligand titration curves were well below the metal ion hydrolysis curves. Hydrolysis of the free metal ions is noticed at pH 4.7, 4.0 and 4.3 for Al^{III}, In^{III}, Ga^{III} respectively, in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water at 35° and $I = 0.1 M$ NaClO₄. However in the presence of chelating agents the hydrolysis of the metal ions has been observed at a higher pH than in the absence of the chelating agent (as indicated by the appearance of turbidity or precipitate) suggesting the stabilisation of metal ions towards hydrolysis due to chelation. The low concentration of metal ions ($10^{-4} M$) used, likely hampers the formation of polynuclear complexes.

The $\bar{n}$ values ($0.1 < \bar{n} < 1.9$) obtained for the metal-ligand systems indicate the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The metal-ligand formation constants have been evaluated by various computational techniques like half-integral, pointwise calculations, linear plots and least-square methods. The values so obtained are in good agreement with each other. The standard deviations for the proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants are within ± 0.03 .

The small differences between log K_1 and log K_2 suggest the simultaneous formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 chelates in solution.

The distribution diagrams drawn for the various species indicate the formation of both ML and ML₂ complexes in significant proportions. As a typical case the distribution curves for the Al^{III}-FHMBANIL system are given in Fig. 1. Similar results were obtained for other systems. Thus, the quantities of M(III) and ML₂ changed monotonically as a function of free ligand concentration, whereas the amount of the intermediate species (ML) attained a certain maximum value.

The stability of metal chelates with all the ligands in the investigation are found to be in the order: Ga^{III} > In^{III} > Al^{III} with respect to log K_1 and log K_2 values (Table 1). The increase in the stability from Al^{III} to Ga^{III} complexes is in accordance with the decreasing order of charge density. Al^{III} because of its small size and high charge density gets extensively solvated compared to indium and gallium ions in the order and therefore forms complexes with less stability. The stability order of complexes with respect to the ligands is FHMBMANIL > FHMBANIL

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for Al^{III}-FHMBANIL system.

>FHMBCANIL, and this is in accordance with the relative basicities of the ligands.

The values of thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) associated with the formation of metal-FHMBMANIL complexes in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water have been determined from the pH metric data at different temperatures (Table 2). The negative free energy change (ΔG) for the metal-FHMBMANIL

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH M(III)-FHMBMANIL CHELATE SYSTEMS IN 70% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL

Temp. = 35°, $I = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

	log K_1			$-\Delta G$ MJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ MJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	25°	35°	45°			
log K_{OH}	8.98	8.92	8.56	—	—	—
log K_{NH^+}	3.54	3.50	3.40	—	—	—
Al ^{III}	7.96	7.68	7.17	45.22	49.15	12.74
In ^{III}	8.86	8.56	8.11	50.41	52.66	7.31
Ga ^{III}	9.07	8.76	8.23	51.58	54.42	9.19

reaction in each case indicates that the chelation is spontaneous. The negative values of enthalpy change (ΔH) indicate exothermic nature of chelation and their magnitude suggests strong metal-ligand bond. The formation of metal complexes by chelation is generally associated with positive entropy changes due to release of bound water molecules from the hydration sphere of metal ions. The negative values of entropy can be attributed to the extensive solvation of metal chelates in aquo-organic media⁶.

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